

BEHAVIOUR PROBLEMS AND NEED FOR BEHAVIOUR MODIFICATION COUNSELLING TECHNIQUES IN THE PRIMARY SCHOOL

Obi, Joy Sylvia Chisara (PhD)¹, Obineli, Susana Uzoamka (PhD)², Akpojivi, Ovie Bright³

¹Department of Guidance and Counselling
Faculty of Education
Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka
Email : js.Obi@unizik.edu.ng

²Department of Guidance and Counselling
Faculty of Education
Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka
Email : su.obineli@unizik.edu.ng

Nigerian Postal Service
Benin Zone

³Email: brightovio@Gmail.com / brightovio_2003@yahoo.Com

INTRODUCTION

Guidance and counseling is aimed at helping individuals understand themselves and their environment so that they can function effectively in the society. It is aimed at helping individuals overcome their problems. The primary school child in Nigeria does not seem to have been exposed to proper and professional guidance and counseling, hence, his or her focus is limited as far as his personality is concerned. According to Idowu (1989), Counseling is a process through which an individual who needs help is assisted by a professionally prepared individual so that he can be helped to make necessary adjustment to life, and to his environment. In the same vein, the school counsellor can help primary school children with behaviour problems. It is a process whereby an individual is helped through a relationship with a professionally prepared person to voluntarily change his behaviour, clarify his attitudes and goals so that his problems could be solved.

Many societies consider behaviour problem such as delinquency, truancy, absenteeism, bullying, violence, drug and alcohol abuse, smoking, and early patterns of sexual behaviour that risk sexually transmitted diseases and pregnancy among never married teenagers to be serious problems. These problems can ruin primary school children and adolescents' lives by leading them to be put in jail, by limiting their education and vocational training opportunities, by having unwanted children, and by risking the development of serious illnesses. In addition, these problems are costly to a society in economic terms. Crime, drug and alcohol abuse, smoking and high-risk

sexual behaviour result in huge health care, judicial and victim-related costs over the life span of children with serious behaviour problems. This chapter examines behaviour problems in primary schools and its need for behaviour modification counselling techniques in the primary school.

Definition of Behaviour Problems

Many children display inappropriate or behaviour problem in the classroom which can make it difficult for them to learn, cause harm to the child or others and isolate the child from his or her peers. Psychologist and counsellor often speak of behaviours problem in terms of the effects they have on others. Therefore, we may label behaviours as "noncompliant" (e.g., when a child refuses to join a class activity), "disrespectful" (e.g., when a child uses bad language) "aggressive" (e.g., when a child throws a book). It will be pertinent to define what behaviour is then proceed to define the compound word behaviour problem.

Kauffman (2013), defined behaviour as the way in which an individual behaves or acts. It is the way an individual conducts herself/himself. The term behaviour refers to the way a person responds to a certain situation or experience. Behaviour is affected by temperament, which is made up of an individual's innate and unique expectations, emotions and beliefs. Behaviour can also be influenced by a range of social and environmental factors including parenting practices, gender, exposure to new situations, general life events and relationships with friends and siblings (Charton, & David, .2006).

Behaviour, therefore, is the way an individual acts towards people, society or objects. It can be either bad or good. It can be normal or abnormal according to society norms. Society will always try to correct bad behaviour and try to bring abnormal behaviour back to normal. In the school setting any act or action that is against the acceptable behaviour in the school is labeled a behaviour problem. In order word behaviour problem are unacceptable actions exhibit by school children.

In a school, there are rules which govern everyday operations, and all school members have to adhere to them. Any school child who deviates from these rules has misbehaved, and is usually reprimanded or punished. Such a pupils is also qualifies as having a behaviour problem. Much behaviour may be considered normal, abnormal, or disordered. A non-disturbed boy or girl does everything that a disturbed boy or girl does. . For example, crying, fighting, screaming, urinating, shouting, are all behaviour indulged in by non-disturbed boys and girls. These are also indulged in by disordered or disturbed boys and girls, but to different degrees. The behaviour of a non-

disturbed boy or girl is usually regarded as reasonable and acceptable by the community. However, that of a disordered boy/girl goes beyond what is considered normal, and is regarded as abnormal and unacceptable (UNESCO, 2000).

Causes of Behaviour Problems in Primary School

According to Barrera, Biglan, Ary and Li (2001) 12 causes of behaviour problems in school child are itemized below;

1. The child is tired
2. The child is physically ill
3. The child is angry or unhappy
4. The child is very happy and excited
5. The child's parents (married or divorced) are squabbling
6. A major change disrupts stable routine
7. Surrounded or "pushed" by intense, nervous, rushing adults
8. Exposed to too much anger, disapproval and unhappiness from others
9. Too much time separated from home or parent
10. Someone (another child or an adult) modeling inappropriate behavior
11. Parents too disconnected from the child on an emotional level
12. The child is not provided with appropriate boundaries and lacks sufficiently close supervision

Pupils are likely to behave in the way they do because of the challenges they face. School counsellors should also appreciate that there are many conflicting and widening choices in the modern world. William (2014), discuss the following as the cause of behaviour problems among school children

a) Mass Media Television shows, video shows, movies and magazines glamourize the behaviour and values of conspicuous models that are incompatible with the standards of many schools rules and regulations as well as families. Imitation of these models results in school authorities and parental disapproval.

b) The Community Religious groups may preach against certain behaviour that is normal in the larger community (e.g. dancing and dating). Children and young people who conform to these religious teachings may be rejected by peers, stigmatized or socially isolated, while those who violate religious teaching may feel extreme guilt.

c) Intermarriages Children of inter-racial marriages may have difficulty developing a sense of identity, especially during adolescence. They may have major problems reconciling their mixed blood into a single, personal identity that affirms the positive aspects of each heritage, while acknowledging society's ambivalence towards bi-racial persons.

d) Teenage Sexuality In the area of sexuality, consider the cultural forces that foster teenage pregnancy, and society's responses to it. Sexual morals have changed over the years, so that adolescents now have much greater freedom and greater responsibility for preventing pregnancy. Society today tempts adolescents and offers them freedoms and responsibilities they are not equipped to handle, yet does nothing to help them deal with them, and punishes them for abusing freedom and behaving irresponsibly. Teenagers often pressure their peers to become sexually active, while conservative politicians attempt to restrict sex education, and make contraceptives less readily available to teenagers. Education for family life and child rearing is not widely available. The many pressures on teenage girls to become sexually active and to become pregnant (i.e., the presence of sugar daddies) and the penalties teenage mothers must pay, must be taken into account. The conflict that exists between cultural and social inducements for teenagers to become sexually active, and the penalties teenage parents pay in the form of limited education, employment and health risks for mothers and children, cannot be ignored. Cultural beliefs and taboos inhibit giving sex education to children. There are other problems which expose pupils to either new hopes or none at all. They may cause increased stress and create more conflicts as pupils grapple with new challenges.

These other aspects include: child abuse, ambitions/aspirations, rural-urban migration, parental separations, broken homes/divorces, being homeless and orphaned, lack of information on sex, living with people of the opposite sex, racism, and recognition of minority groups as identified by (UNESCO, 2000)

The Role of School in a Child Developing Behaviour Problem

The school has probably the most important socializing influence on children and young people. One need to examine carefully the role of the school in the development of behaviour, because the school environment is where the teacher, educators and school administrators have direct control. Conditions outside the school can influence student behaviour in school. Some children do develop certain behaviour before they begin school. But if a child already has a behaviour problems, the school counsellor should consider how the school might decrease or eliminate it. Many children, for example, do not show behaviour disorders until they go to school. Again, one must consider the possibility that the school is the cause of this. An ecological approach to understanding behaviour includes the assumption that all aspects of a child's environment are intermingled. Changes in one element of the ecology have implications for the others. For example, success or failure in school affects behaviour at home and in the community. Consequently, success at school assumes even greater importance if a child's home and community environments are disadvantaged. One should consider the elimination of possible school contributions to behaviour before labelling pupils adversely. Schools can contribute to disorders. Below average intelligence and inadequate academic achievement are characteristic of pupils with behaviour disorders. Conduct disorder, low intelligence and achievement, provide gloomy elements for adulthood. Although school failure is not known to cause behaviour disorders, it usually goes hand in hand with maladjusted behaviour. On the other hand, it can be argued that maladjusted behaviour makes academic success unlikely and contributes to school failure. Logically, it can be accepted that the school can contribute to both social difficulties and academic incompetence. The demands of the school and a pupil's social and academic ability probably affect each other. Pupils who are healthy, intelligent, socio-economically advantaged, with good self-esteem and interpersonal skills, attract others to respond to them positively. These advantaged pupils are sensitive to the responses of others towards them and are able to use their intelligence to enhance their personal power and social status. Intelligence and achievement produce acceptability, self-esteem, accurate social perception and status, and in turn induce positive social responses from others and facilitate achievement. On the other hand, pupils with conduct disorders are caught in negative reinforcement traps among their peers, and in their interactions with teachers and administrators. Teachers (like parents), and classroom peers (like siblings), can become entangled in escalating contests of aversion, in which the individual who causes the greater pain is the winner. How the

school affects a pupil's emotional or behavioural development depends on his or her characteristics when entering the educational system. The same type of interaction between the pupil's temperament and the parent's child-rearing techniques also occurs between the pupil's temperament and the social and academic demands of the school. The student who is slow to approach others, has irregular working habits, is slow to adapt to situations, and is predominantly negative in mood, is most likely to have difficulty in school. Any temperamental characteristic is susceptible to modification. The school, as with family and biological factors, does not affect behaviour unilaterally to determine the pupil's behavioural development. But classroom conditions, and teacher reactions to pupil behaviour, make behavioural problems more likely to occur, or reduce the likelihood of behaviour disorder developing.

There are six ways in which the school can contribute to the development of disordered behaviour and academic failure:

- a) insensitivity to pupils' individuality;
- b) inappropriate pupil expectations;
- c) inconsistent management of behaviour;
- d) instruction in non-functional and irrelevant skills;
- e) destructive contingencies of reinforcement;
- f) undesirable models of school conduct.

One must be prepared to work with pupils who are intellectually and academically deficient, as well as deviant in their social behaviour. As a preventive agent, one's tasks are to foster success and lessen the student's anti-social conduct by making his life more meaningful. Academic failure and anti-social behaviour presage limited future opportunities and probably future maladjustment.

Goals Of Primary School Counselling

Primary school counselling focuses on the child a learner and on the teachers as helpers. Its goals, therefore, has wide Implications for children (pupils) and teachers, as highlighted below as cited by Idowu (1986):

- (a) The Counsellor assists each child to understand and accept his uniqueness and liabilities.
- (b) The counsellor helps the child to develop a healthy self concept.
- (c) The counsellor helps the child to grow and develop in all spheres of life.
- (d) The counsellor helps the child to deal with normal and interpersonal relationships.
- (e) The counsellor assists the child to cope with and alleviate personal and emotional problems.

The Counsellor and Primary School Child

The Counsellor as a helping professional should realise that counselling in the primary school is different from counselling in the other stages of the school system. The clients that the guidance/counsellor deal with at the primary school state are younger than those in the higher levels of the educational system. Many of them are between the ages of six and twelve years. The counsellor should therefore understand the characteristics of these children. Specifically, he should understand their behaviours and know them very well, so that he can counsel them effectively. To do this he has to put into practice all the theories he has learnt as a school counsellor.

First, he should be highly empathic, so that he can succeed in his bid to provide counselling services in primary schools. He should know the feelings of these young people and try as much as possible to share their feelings and understand to share their feelings and understand their problems. Some of them may not be as verbal as the counsellor would expect.

Through his empathic disposition, he/she will be able to observe and understand his non-verbal clients and to interpret their feelings in the most professional manner. Moreover, the counselor should be patient. He has to be actively involved in the counselling relationship. He has to give the young clients his total attention, so that he may be able to get at the root cause of their problems. Further, the primary school counsellor should establish and maintain a good rapport and cordial relationship, with his clients. He has to exhibit a very sound moral character. He cannot, afford to behave irrationally among the young clients. He has to be an individual who will inspire emulation, because young people very easily emulate the older ones.

Essence of Primary School Counseling

Essence of Primary School Counseling, Hardly does a primary school child volunteer as a counselling client. This is due to immaturity in thought patterns of the children at that level. This copious fact adds however, to the tasks of the primary school counsellor who is expected to be selective in his counselling strategies (Egbo, 2015). To a large extent for example, the client centred theory at the elementary school level is 'doctored' because the school child can hardly

think decisively for themselves. Thus behaviour modification strategies and techniques in operant, classical and modeling theories; observational techniques as well as play therapy techniques are implored in counselling the children.

Behaviour among school children that are rewarded easily keep reoccurring, while extinction also, can take place appropriately. The implication is that counsellors should device effective, efficacious and related techniques to eliminates totally or weaken deviant behaviours. The childs' feelings, emotions and interest should be highly considered and close working relationship with parents would significantly increase the wellbeing of the child. The counsellor should be able to pick nonverbal, and or verbal cues which are significant in any counselling processes to help the elementary school client. Besides, the counsellor would also strive to seek for clients than sit back and wait for clients because of the immaturity of the school children. As well, the counsellor should be good in record keeping. Krumboltz and Horseford in Egbo (2012) write that counselling techniques at the primary school are really devised to fit individuals as at times, the pupils are helped to make good decisions by learning to:

1. Construct alternative behaviour
2. Seek relevant information about alternatives
3. Weigh values and possible outcomes and
4. Formulates tentative plans of action

The counsellor therefore is expected to emphasis therapeutic principles in counseling the pupils with behaviour problems. The primary school children therefore need counselling for the following reasons:

1. Need to tap and harness the individual pupils' ability, interest, personality, talents and aptitude starts at this level for their developmental growth.
2. Need to provide special help for numerous primary school children to avert possible crimes and health hazards
3. Need to stem the tide of maladaptive behaviours in the school system and the general public
4. Need to identify and nurture the gifted and talented children

5. Need for behavioural changes as many homes now breed social problems
6. Need for outreach counselling especially as many homes are impoverished
7. Need to provide the child with a sound foundation for future, academic, psychological and personal growth

The need for counselling at the primary school system, according to Durojaiye in Egbo (2008) emanate from the fact that the Nigerian family had experienced significant changes that had resulted in breakdown of family cohesiveness and increased rate of divorce. This has significantly increased the one parent home trend and subsequent increment in deviant behaviours among children because:

1. Divorce and its accompanying strains continue to increase
2. Children are being reared differently and more frequently by outsiders (maids or day care givers)
3. Mothers are plagued by the guilt of leaving their children to go to work
4. Parents generally do not have time to monitor their primary school children. Consequently, primary school teachers and counsellors need to understand the unique characteristics and nature of each pupil as well as be able to make relative referrals at any point in time. Good classroom and social and social climate should be created for inclusive development of the pupils for maximum sustenance of solutions to academic, vocational and personal social problems of the Nigerian primary school pupil.

Behaviour Modification Techniques Used By Primary School Counsellor In Enhancing Behaviour Problems

According to Mather and Goldstein (2013) Behaviour modification assumes that observable and measurable behaviors are good targets for change. All behaviour follows a set of consistent rules. Methods can be developed for defining, observing, and measuring behaviors, as well as designing effective interventions. Behaviour modification techniques never fail. Rather, they are either applied inefficiently or inconsistently, which leads to less than desired change. All behaviour is maintained, changed, or shaped by the consequences of that behaviour. Reinforcers are

consequences that strengthen behavior. Punishments are consequences that weaken behavior. Students' behaviors are managed and changed by the consequences of classroom behavior. To manage behaviour through consequences, use this multi-step process:

1. The problem must be defined, usually by count or description.
2. Design a way to change the behavior.
3. Identify an effective reinforcer.
4. Apply the reinforcer consistently to shape or change behavior.

Consequences of behavior are directly related to the events that either come immediately before or after them. Table 1.1 provides examples of behavioural outcomes as they relate to various events.

Table 4.1. Popular models and techniques for dealing with discipline referrals	
Model	Techniques emphasized
Focusing on Prevention	
Preventative classroom management	Effective teaching practices, frequent monitoring, clear rules and procedures, social praise, and so forth
Prosocial behavior	Systematic reinforcement, modeling of prosocial behavior, verbal instruction, role playing

Moral education	Classroom moral discussions of real-life dilemmas, hypothetical situations, and literature; role playing; student participation in school government
Social problem solving (SPS)	Direct teaching of SPS skills (e.g. alternative thinking, means-ends thinking), self- instruction training, dialoguing
Effective communication models	Values clarification activities, active listening, communication and interpersonal skills training for students and teachers
Focusing on Correction and Control of Misbehavior	
Behavior modification	Direct instruction; reinforcement techniques, including social praise, material reinforcers, and tokens; punishment-oriented techniques, including verbal reprimand, response cost, and time-out; group contingency techniques such as the Good Behavior Game; behavioral contracting
Assertive discipline	Teacher assertion, systematic use of behavior modification techniques, continuous monitoring
Reality therapy	Confrontation questioning, classroom meetings, classroom moral discussions, social problem solving, behavioral contracting, logical consequences, time-out, preventative techniques such as democratic governance

Focus on Treatment	
Social skills training	Direct instruction, modeling and rehearsal, coaching, self-instruction, manipulation of antecedents and consequences
Aggression replacement training	Social skills training techniques, self- instruction (e.g. anger control training), moral discussions
Parent management training	Parent training in application of behavioral techniques
Family therapy	Variety of therapeutic and educational techniques, depending on the particular model
Behavior therapy	Variety of cognitive, behavioral, and operant techniques

Reinforcement and punishment follow a clear set of basic principles:

1. reinforcement or punishment always follows behavior,
2. reinforcement or punishment follows the target behavior as soon as possible,
3. reinforcement or punishment fits the target behavior and must be meaningful to the child, and
4. multiple reinforcers, or punishments are likely more effective than single reinforcers or punishments.

Reinforcement

Table 1.2. Technique, behavior, consequence, and probable effect

Classification	Exhibited behavior	Consequences	Probable future effect on behavior
Positive reinforcement	Jane cleans her room.	Jane's parents praise her.	Jane will continue to clean her room.
Positive reinforcement	Carmen brushes her teeth after meals.	Carmen receives a nickel each time.	Carmen will continue to brush her teeth after meals.
Positive reinforcement	Rob works quietly at his seat.	The teacher praises and rewards Rob.	Rob will continue to work quietly at his seat.
Negative reinforcement	Jason complains that older boys consistently beat him up, and he refuses to attend school.	Jason's parents allow him to remain at home because of his complaints.	Jason will continue to miss school.

Negative reinforcement	Balin complains of headaches when it is time to do homework.	Balin is allowed to go to bed without doing his homework.	Balin will have headaches whenever there is homework to do.
Extinction	Jim washes his father's car.	Jim's car washing behavior is ignored.	Jim will stop washing his father's car.
Extinction	Carmen puts glue on Joe's seat.	Carmen is ignored.	Carmen will stop putting glue on Joe's seat.
Punishment	Marta sits on the arm of the chair.	Marta is spanked each time she sits on the arm of the chair.	Marta will not sit on the arm of the chair.
Punishment	Takeo puts Gwen's pigtails in the paint.	The teacher administers the paddle to Takeo's posterior.	Takeo will not put Gwen's pigtail in the paint.

A number of simple, effective ways exist to deal with this problem. If you are using negative reinforcement, pay attention to the student until the assignment is completed. Although this too is negative reinforcement, it teaches the child that the only way to get rid of the aversive consequence (i.e. your attention) is not just to start but to complete the task at hand. As an example, you may move the student's desk next to your desk until that particular piece of work is completed.

A second alternative involves the use of differential attention or ignoring. The term differential attention applies when ignoring is used as the negative consequence for exhibiting the undesirable behavior, and attention is used as a positive consequence for exhibiting the competing desirable behavior. This is an active process in which the teacher ignores the child engaged in an off-task activity but pays attention immediately when the child begins working. Many teachers avoid interaction with the child when he or she is on task for fear of interrupting the child's train of thought. It is important, however, to reinforce the child when working so that a pattern of working to earn positive reinforcement rather than working to avoid negative reinforcement is developed. Secondary school teachers at times complain that if they ignore the adolescent with

Modeling

Through modeling, observation, and then imitation, children develop new behaviors. Modeling can be as simple as having a child watch another child sharpen a pencil. By watching the model, a child can learn a new behavior, inhibit another behavior, or strengthen previously learned behavior (e.g. saying "thank you"). To use modeling effectively, you must determine whether a child has the capacity to observe and then imitate the model. In classroom settings, a student's response to modeling is influenced by three factors: 1) the characteristics of the model (e.g. is this a student whom the other students like and respect?), 2) the characteristics of the observer (e.g. is this child capable of observing and imitating the behavior), and 3) the positive or negative consequences associated with the behavior. Children are more likely to respond to teacher modeling when they view their teachers as competent, nurturing, supportive, fun, and interesting. Children are also more likely to imitate behavior that results in a positive consequence.

Younger children have been reported as more frequently imitating others than older children. Children consistently model someone whom they value or look up to. They also imitate the behavior of a same-sex child more often than that of a different-sex child. They model someone whom they perceive as successful and socially valued regardless of whether the teacher perceives

that child as successful and socially valued. Finally, if a child observes a model being reinforced or punished for certain behavior, this influences the likelihood that the child will then model that behavior.

Modeling is a powerful tool, often underutilized by teachers. When teachers are cheerful and enthusiastic, their attitudes are contagious. When they are respectful of students, students respect each other. When teachers are patient, fair, consistent, and optimistic, their students exhibit these traits as well. Teacher behavior sets the tone for the classroom environment.

Shaping

Waiting for the appropriate target behavior or something close to that behavior to occur before reinforcing the behavior is referred to as shaping. Shaping can be used to establish behaviors that are not routinely exhibited. Walker and Shea (2014) described the steps to effective shaping:

1. Select a target behavior and define it.
2. Observe how often the behavior is exhibited.
3. Select reinforcers.
4. Decide on close approximations and reinforce successive approximations to the target behavior each time it occurs.
5. Reinforce the newly established behavior.
6. Reinforce the old behavior on a variable schedule, and begin reinforcing the new behavior on an every-time or continuous schedule. The key to successful shaping is to reinforce closer approximations and not reinforce lesser approximations.

Any behavior that remotely resembles the target behavior should initially be reinforced. Prompts can be used and then faded. Shaping can be used for all kinds of behavior in the classroom, including academics. Steps toward successive approximation, however, must be carefully thought out; otherwise, behaviors that are not working toward the desired goal may inadvertently be reinforced.

Punishment

Punishment suppresses undesirable behavior but may not necessarily eliminate it). In some cases, suppression may be of short duration, and when the punishment is removed, the behavior may

reoccur. Punishment can involve presentation of an unpleasant consequence or the loss of a pleasurable consequence following the occurrence of the undesirable behavior. Punishment is designed to reduce the probability that the behavior that precedes it will reoccur. Although punishment is an efficient way of changing behavior, it can become seductive and reinforcing for classroom teachers and can be overused. The greatest problem with punishment is that it does not provide an appropriate model of acceptable behavior. Furthermore, in many classrooms, punishment is accompanied by an emotional response from the teacher. Although most teachers consider punishment as involving a reprimand, time-out, or loss of an activity such as recess, in many classrooms, physical punishment designed to embarrass children into submission is still used, even though it has a high emotional cost. Walker and Shea (2014) made a strong case for minimizing the use of punishment, especially more severe punishment, such as embarrassment or spanking, because these interventions are likely to erode self-esteem and further impair an already strained teacher-student relationship. When punishments are used, these guidelines should be followed:

1. All students are aware of which behaviors are punished and how they are punished.
2. Appropriate models for acceptable behavior are provided.
3. Punishments are offered immediately, consistently, and fairly.
4. Punishments are offered impersonally.
5. A natural or logical consequence should be used as often as possible.
6. The student being punished must understand the relationship between his or her behavior and the punishment.

Loss of the privilege during which the inappropriate behavior is exhibited is fair. Warning, nagging, threatening, and debating, however, should be avoided. In other words, act, don't yak. Punishment can exert a complex, negative effect in the classroom and on teacher-student relationships. Furthermore, when less punishing interventions are combined with positive reinforcers, they tend to be effective in the long run. In 1946, Anderson and Brewer reported that teachers using dominating behaviors of force, threat, shame, and blame had classrooms in which children displayed nonconforming behavior at rates higher than in classrooms in which teachers were more positive and supportive. Personal hostility from teachers and punishments in an atmosphere containing minimal positive reinforcement and emotional warmth are unproductive.

To be effective, punishment must be related in form to the misbehavior. It must be consistent, fair, and just; must be delivered impersonally; and must not involve the assignment of extra work that is unrelated to the act for which the student is being punished. Opportunities must also be offered for the student to exhibit and receive reinforcement for more appropriate behavior.

Response cost

Response cost is a punishing technique that translates to the equivalent of losing what you possess or have earned. Earned consequences are considered reinforcers. When they are lost, this is response cost. The child places in jeopardy what he or she has earned as the result of inappropriate behavior. In many situations, response cost in the form of a penalty or fine is combined with positive reinforcement. To be effective, more reinforcers must be earned than lost. Response cost is often used to reduce off-task behavior and improve compliance with directions.

Time-out

Time-out from reinforcement excludes children from the opportunity to participate with others and receive any kind of positive reinforcement. Time-out is by far the best known disciplinary technique among teachers. It is also the most likely to be overused and misused in the classroom. Although a brief time-out of a few minutes duration can exert a positive influence on classroom behavior when applied appropriately, many teachers apply time-out ineffectively as often as effectively (Rhode, Jenson & Reavis, (2014)).

Conclusion

The effective use of behaviour modification techniques in the classroom may appear daunting even to experienced teachers. However, changing your behaviour and strategies is often the most efficient and effective means of improving all types of classroom behaviors, both disruptive and non-disruptive behaviour. Through practice comes proficiency. The building block of emotions and behavior likely contains the largest and most diverse set of problems encountered in the classroom. By first understanding these problems and seeing the world through the eyes of your students, and, by then developing and using a set of intervention strategies on a regular basis, problems of emotions and behavior can be effectively

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